

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Develop and support a flexible, efficient and secure end-to-end digital Privacy and Personal Data Protection (PDP) compliance framework and Identity Management System (IdMS) for SMEs/MEs

Provide technological advances in automated data protection compliance assessment, such as tailor-made automated requirements engineering as a service, Machine Learning anomaly detection & recommendation systems and a Unified IdMS

Provide novel tools and services for enabling highly automated PDP compliance in SMEs/MEs

Validate, demonstrate and carry out experimental evaluation of the proposed framework on real-world SMEs/MEs operation scenarios

Raise awareness, collaborate with standardisation bodies and ensure technology transfer of project's results via EU digital innovation hubs

Boost the effectiveness of the EU data economy by offering high Technology Readiness Level solutions (TRL 6-7)

USE CASES

ClinGenics - A microenterprise

Implementing extra security measures for accessing genomic sequence and personal data from a bioinformatics platform-software pipeline.

Tristone Investment Group - An SME

Homogenising the approach to data protection and compliance across multiple portfolio businesses through a single platform

UNINOVA - SMEs/MEs engaged via Digital Innovation Hubs

Assessment of compliance regarding privacy and personal data protection within an ecosystem of SMEs and MEs

Consortium

The consortium consists of 14 partners from ten (10) European countries: Greece, Luxembourg, Belgium, Ireland, Switzerland, Germany, France, Portugal, United Kingdom and Malta.

- ITML
- Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology
- The Shell Company
- Institute of Digital Innovation and Research Limited
- Intrasoft S.A.
- Sphynx Technology Solutions
- Aegis IT research GMBH
- Telecommunication Systems Institute
- Airbus Cybersecurity SAS
- UNINOVA - Instituto de Desenvolvimento de Novas Tecnologias
- Clingenics (UK) LTD
- Tristone Investment Group Limited
- Centre for European Constitutional Law
- Focal Point

SENTINEL CONCEPT & APPROACH

The SENTINEL project will deliver a solution that will enable a novel “one-stop shop” approach to integrated and obtainable private and personal data protection compliance for SMEs/MEs.

This will be achieved through the adherence to the following project propositions:

Deliver a robust, technologically feasible and usable digital architecture that will provide SMEs/MEs security and privacy functionalities hitherto unavailable outside the domain of large enterprises.

Offer its users a theoretically relevant detailed methodology for the effective utilisation of this digital framework.

Allow for extensive experimentation on three carefully chosen pilots from three different business domains featuring sensitive personal data protection requirements.

Roll out this novel approach to over 10.000 smaller enterprises across at least 6 countries, in numerous verticals, through the consortium's ambitious dissemination, communication and exploitation plan.

1st Sentinel SME engagement workshop @ Guimarães, Portugal

As part of SENTINEL's first plenary meeting, we organized our first SME engagement workshop from a series of workshops that will be conducted regularly throughout the project lifetime.

Considering that Sentinel aims to: “Develop and support a flexible, efficient and secure end-to-end digital Privacy and Personal Data Protection (PDP) compliance framework and Identity Management System (IdMS) for SMEs/MEs”, there is a need to start engaging SMEs and MEs from an early stage of the project.

Supported by UNINOVA with the collaboration from Universidade do Minho, this workshop was held on the 16th of September 2021 in Guimarães at CCG (Centro de Computação Gráfica) facilities.

Guimarães is located in a region called “Vale do Ave”, which is characterized by a strong presence of companies related to the textile, shoe and steel manufacturing industry, including supplying and other companies from the manufacturing supply chain.

Due to Covid-19 restrictions, the participation of SMEs was limited considering the workshop venue capacity, nevertheless, more than 10 SMEs participated, ranging from the textile, shoe, heavy machinery and IT domain areas.

During the Q&A session, SMEs representatives had the opportunity to express their concerns and get feedback with regard to their internal policies and IT infrastructure towards addressing data security, privacy and protection.

Some initial insights obtained from the workshop show that:

- Some SMEs are facing procedural issues regarding data;
- Some SMEs are facing lack of efficient IT infrastructure and services;
- Some SMEs are facing both.

Project Management Board

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Project Coordinator: Dr George Bravos
Institution: INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY FOR MARKET LEADERSHIP (ITML)
Email: gebravos@itml.gr
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Number of countries: 10

@SentinelH2020

company/sentinel-eu-project/

sentinelh2020@gmail.com

www.sentinel-project.eu/

